

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

Qualitative Study on Implementation of Public Primary Schools Early Childhood Care Education Programs in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

Ahmed, Tunde Abdulganiyu¹

ahmedydefirst@gmail.com

08066656426

Enokela, Onum Maria²

mariaonumenokela@gmail.com

07030423778

Okoh, Martha¹

Marthaokoh544@gmail.com

07036718450

Idoko, Charity¹

Idokocharity2013@gmail.com

070325121580423778

¹Department of Primary Education Studies, Federal College of Education, Odugbo, Benue State

²Department of Early Childhood Care Education, Federal College of Education, Odugbo, Benue State

Abstract

This study examined the implementation of public primary schools early childhood care education programs in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design which was carried out in 12 randomly selected public primary schools in Abuja. 309 respondents were sampled using multi-stage sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was researcher adapted 40-item questionnaire titled Public Primary Schools Early Childhood Care Education Programs (PPSECCEP) with a reliability coefficient of 0.92. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. However, a key finding indicated that most parents and society lacked adequate awareness of ECCE programs' significance. While staff demonstrated necessary skills, facility provisions for program implementation were insufficient. Based on these findings, the study recommends awareness campaigns to increase parental and societal support, staff incentives to enhance service delivery, and regular facility assessments to address resource gaps.

Keywords: Early Childhood Program, Effectiveness, Examined, Implementation & Primary Schools

Introduction

In our daily observations of children, we can identify childhood as the time when we are not responsible for anything and rely on adults for protection and care. It is also the period we learn mostly through play and imitation. The childhood stage begins at birth and lasts until puberty, usually between 10 and 12 years of age. As society's ideas about childhood change over time, research has led to a better understanding of each stage's development. Childhood period has been universally acknowledged as a period when development of an individual is most crucial. Early childhood comprises a number of life stages, marked by developmental milestones. Early childhood is a time of bridge building. It is a time in a child's life when bridges are built between the shelter of home and the demands of the school; between play with a few neighborhood friends and relationship with many children. It is that period of human development which falls between birth to eight years (birth-8 years). The time from birth to eight years is a critical period in the development of many foundational skills in all areas of development. This is the time when environmental enrichment or deprivation makes its greatest impact. It is a period marked with significant changes and reorganizations in the child's behaviour. At this period a lot of changes and progress are made in terms of learning, reasoning and in the child's social relationship with others. It is indeed the period the child gains a sense of self-worth, or lack of it, and confidence, or lack of confidence, as he experiences success or failure in everyday contacts.

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

Early childhood education as contained in the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2004) is the education given in an educational institution to children prior to their entering the primary school. Maduwesi (1999) as cited by Ogunode et al. (2021) defines early childhood education as a semi-formal education arrangement, usually outside the home, whereby young children from about the age of three are exposed, through play-like activities in a group setting, to mental, social and physical learning suited to their developmental stage, until the mandatory age of government approved formal schooling. In the same vein, several other terms used to describe early childhood education include nursery school, pre-primary and pre-school. Oduolowu (2003) as cited by Okewole (2009) asserted that early childhood education is part and parcel of education program or package whether formal or informal of every culture. Some schools of thought opined that early childhood education is universal; and that there is no society where human beings exist without early childhood education. Akinola (2004) sees it as the education given in an educational institution to children aged three to five plus prior to entering the primary education. Early Childhood Education is a term that has a scope that varies and is often linked to geographical locations. Different definitions focus on different aspects of the educational experience. Some emphasize the age range of the children involved, while others place more importance on the environment in which the education is delivered. Still others combine both of these elements. Generally, Early Childhood Education refers to pre-school or pre-primary education that is delivered outside of the home in a semi-formal setting. This can include programs like crèches, daycares, nurseries, and kindergartens, and is typically designed for children between the ages of 0 and 5 years.

ECCE is a special field of education for development of children. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) recognizes the importance of ECCE and thereafter, began to explore ways of implementing the Early Childhood Care Education for general development of the child. The purposes of ECCE as stipulated in the National Policy on Education by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013:5) include: to effect a smooth transition from home to the school, prepare the child for the primary level of education, provide adequate care and supervision for the children while their parents are at work, inculcate social norms in the children, inculcate in the children the spirit of enquiry and creativity through the exploration of nature, environment, art, music and playing, develop a sense of co-operation and team spirit, learn good habits, especially good health habits, and teach the rudiments of numbers, letters, colours, shapes and forms through play. These objectives must be implemented in the schools by ECCE proprietors and society.

On this background, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) in Nigeria, with both public and private primary schools incorporating ECCE in their school programs. ECCE refers to a range of services and programs that are designed to promote the development of young children, from birth to age 8, in all areas of their lives, including physical, emotional, social, and cognitive development. While the incorporation of ECCE in primary schools is a positive development, it is not clear whether these ECCE centers are operating within the context of the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) curriculum. The NERDC is the body responsible for developing and implementing curriculum guidelines for all levels of education in Nigeria, including ECCE. The lack of clarity regarding the implementation of ECCE curriculum in Nigeria is a cause for concern. The quality of early childhood education is crucial, as it can have a significant impact on a child's development and future academic success. If ECCE centers are not operating within the context of the NERDC curriculum, there may be inconsistencies in the quality of early childhood education provided to children across the country. To address this issue, the thrust of this study is to assess the qualitative implementation of public primary schools early childhood care education programs in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The study aims to identify gaps in the implementation of ECCE policies, assess the quality of early childhood education provided, and provide recommendations to improve the quality of ECCE in Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) has been identified as a vital component of educational development in Nigeria. Over the years, there has been a growing emphasis on the importance of ECCE in Nigeria as it is believed to play a significant role in laying the foundation for future learning and development (FRN 2012). Of recent, it should be noted that both public primary schools and private primary schools in Nigeria incorporate ECCE in school programs. However, it is not certain whether these ECCE centres are operating within the context of the National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) curriculum. The Nigerian government recognizes the importance of ECCE and has put in place policies and frameworks to promote its implementation (FRN 2013). The Federal Ministry of Education has developed the National Policy on Education, which recognizes ECCE as an integral part of the education system. The policy recommends that ECCE should be provided for children between the ages of 0-5 years (FME, 2013).

Furthermore, the National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) has also developed a curriculum for ECCE (UNESCO, 2007). The curriculum is designed to provide a comprehensive framework for the development of children in the

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

areas of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. The curriculum covers various aspects of child development such as language, literacy, numeracy, science, social studies, creative arts, and physical education.

Despite the existence of these policies and frameworks, there are still gaps in the implementation of ECCE in Nigeria (Akinrotimi & Olowe, 2016). One of the major challenges is the lack of adequate funding for ECCE programs (Amadi, 2013). Many ECCE centres are poorly equipped (Akinrotimi & Olowe, 2016), and teachers are often poorly trained (Olaleye & Omotayo, 2009), which affects the quality of the education provided. In addition, there is a lack of awareness among parents and society about the importance of ECCE, which often leads to low enrollment rates. Many parents in Nigeria still believe that the primary responsibility of childcare and early education lies with the family and not with the school.

Against this background, a comprehensive ECCE curriculum was designed for implementation to equip the children with the desired skills needed for effective primary education and social life. And it is however uncertain whether these schools are implementing the curriculum. It is on this premise that the thrust of this paper is predicated to assess the effectiveness of the implementation of public primary schools' early childhood care education program in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study is undertaken to:

- (i) Investigate the extent to which ECCE programs benefit public primary school children in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
- (ii) Determine the level of adequate awareness among parents and society regarding the importance of ECCE programs in public primary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
- (iii) Explore the extent to which staff possesses the necessary skills to effectively implement the ECCE program in public primary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
- (iv) Ascertain the level of the availability and adequacy of the facilities required for the implementation of the ECCE program in public primary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- (i) To what extent does an ECCE program beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?
- (ii) To what extent do parents and society lack adequate awareness of ECCE programs in public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?
- (iii) To what extent does staff have the required skills to implement the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?
- (iv) What is the level of availability and adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is descriptive survey research. The study population comprised head teachers, classroom teachers, parents of early childhood education centers, and Ministry of Education officials in Abuja. According to the Open Education Data (2023), there are 1573 schools that include nursery and primary levels in Abuja, Nigeria. However, the target population for this study consisted all the 597 Public Primary Schools in Abuja, the sample for the study comprised 309 respondents (www.raosoft.com/samplesizecalculator), consisting of 72 head teachers, 144 classroom teachers, 144 parents of early childhood education pupils, and 21 Ministry of Education officials (state the academic session). A multistage sampling technique was adopted to select the sample for the study. The researcher selected 12 public ECCE schools from each stratum (from each Local Government in Abuja) using stratified random sampling technique, from a total of 36 public ECCE schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. From each school selected, 4 head teachers and 8 classroom teachers were selected using purposive sampling technique based on their qualifications as experts in early childhood education, while 4 parents were selected using accidental sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 21 State Ministry of Education officials.

The research instrument for this study was questionnaire adapted by the researcher. The instrument was given to the experts in early childhood education to establish the content validity while experts in test development were consulted for construct validity. The observations and suggestions made by experts were used for the final preparation of the instrument. In computing the reliability of this research instrument, split-half method was employed to test internal consistency of the instrument, the instrument was administered to 40 stakeholders comprising 10 head teachers, 10 ministry officials, 10 classroom

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

teachers and 10 parents. Their responses to the items on this instrument were used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument which yielded a reliability of 0.92. Descriptive analysis was employed to analyze the data collected for this study. Specifically, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the raised research question.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does an ECCE program beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the extent an ECCE program beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	ECCE programs offer the opportunity to socialize with peers and adults.		2.65	0.74	Agreed
2.	Children learn how to interact with others in ECCE centers.		2.71	0.58	Agreed
3.	Children develop social and emotional skills such as empathy, self-awareness, and emotional regulation in ECCE centers.		2.68	0.71	Agreed
4.	ECCE programs provide opportunities to develop cognitive skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and language development.		2.53	0.80	Agreed
5.	ECCE programs laying the foundation for academic success later on.		2.89	0.46	Agreed
6.	ECCE programs promote physical health through healthy meals, opportunities for physical activity, and health screenings.		2.51	0.49	Agreed
7.	ECCE programs develop child pre-academic skills such as numeracy, literacy, and fine motor skills.		2.97	0.64	Agreed
8.	ECCE programs expose children to different cultures, languages, and perspectives, promoting cultural awareness and appreciation.		2.50	0.66	Agreed
9.	ECCE programs foster creativity by providing opportunities for imaginative play, artistic expression, and critical thinking.		2.52	0.50	Agreed
10.	ECCE programs support language development, an essential skill for academic success and communication.		2.70	0.61	Agreed

Source: Author’s Computation, 2023

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the extent to which ECCE programs benefit public primary school children in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The results indicate that respondents perceive these programs as beneficial, with all mean scores (\bar{X}) exceeding the criterion mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 for the 10 items. Notably, no item fell below this criterion. The consistency of responses, reflected by small standard deviation values, suggests a high level of agreement among respondents. Overall, this translates to a decision level of 'great extent,' suggesting the ECCE program is highly beneficial to public primary school children in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Research Question 2: To what extent do parents and society lack adequate awareness of ECCE programs in public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the extent parents and society adequate awareness of ECCE programs in public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	ECCE is a term every parent is familiar with.		2.01	1.16	Disagreed
2.	Early childhood education is considered to be very important for young children		2.22	1.02	Disagreed
3.	Young children need early childhood education to develop properly.		1.93	1.05	Disagreed

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

4.	The long-term effects of ECCE on their child's education and future success are known by parents and society.	1.88	1.11	Disagreed
5.	Parents and society are being educated on how ECCE can support their child's cognitive growth.	2.10	1.23	Disagreed
6.	The significance of ECCE in laying the foundation for child's academic success is recognized by parents and society.	2.12	0.90	Disagreed
7.	Parents and society know the different ECCE programs available and which ones are best suited for child's needs.	1.85	1.01	Disagreed
8.	Parents and society are well-informed about the importance of high-quality ECCE programs for their child.	2.00	1.41	Disagreed
9.	The roles of ECCE in child development are known by parents and society.	1.54	0.42	Disagreed
10.	The value of ECCE in enhancing child's social and emotional development is appreciated to a sufficient extent by parents and society.	1.99	0.67	Disagreed

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

The mean and standard deviation of responses to a 10-item survey were presented in table 2. The findings revealed that the respondents did not perceive parents and society to be sufficiently aware of the importance of ECCE programs, as indicated by mean scores (\bar{X}) that were lower than the criterion mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 for all items. None of the mean scores (\bar{X}) were higher than the criterion mean (\bar{X}). The low standard deviation values indicated a low variation among responses, implying that to a great extent the majority of parents and society lacked adequate awareness about the significance of ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja.

Research Question 3: To what extent does staff have the required skills to implement the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the extent staff have the required skills to implement the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	The staff's have knowledge about the principles and goals of the ECCE programs.		2.51	0.60	Agreed
2.	There is confidence in staff's ability to effectively teach the curriculum of the ECCE programs.		2.73	0.63	Agreed
3.	ECCE staff have received adequate training on the specific teaching methods and techniques required for the ECCE programs.		2.88	0.78	Agreed
4.	ECCE staff are capable of creating a positive and supportive learning environment for children participating in the ECCE programs.		2.50	0.63	Agreed
5.	ECCE programs effective implementation depends on how well the staff works together as a team.		2.50	0.53	Agreed
6.	The ECCE staff have experience working with diverse groups of children and families, as required by the ECCE programs.		2.69	0.42	Agreed
7.	The ECCE staff are familiar with and able to apply the appropriate assessment and evaluation techniques for the ECCE programs.		2.53	0.61	Agreed
8.	ECCE staff received ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge related to the ECCE programs.		2.35	0.42	Disagreed

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

9.	ECCE staff undergo retraining professional development opportunities to upgrade their skills and knowledge related to the ECCE programs.	2.41	0.46	Disagreed
10.	ECCE staff is very effective in communicating and collaborating with families and society of children enrolled in the ECCE programs.	2.19	0.51	Disagreed

Source: Author’s Computation, 2023

The results presented in table 3 show the mean and standard deviation of respondents’ opinion on the extent to which staff possess the required skills to implement the ECCE programs. The results revealed that staff have the necessary skills to implement the ECCE programs, as indicated on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. These items have their mean (\bar{X}) values greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 ($\bar{X} < 2.50$). The values of the standard deviation on the items indicate less variation in the responses of the respondents (teachers) due to the closeness of the values. Items 8, 9 and 10 had mean scores below the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 which indicates that ECCE staff do not undergo retraining professional development to upgrade their skills and knowledge related to the ECCE programs. This implies that the majority of staff members possess the required skills to implement the ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja.

Research Question 4: What is the level of availability and adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of level of availability and adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=144	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs are adequate.		2.12	1.23	Disagreed
2.	There are no any specific facilities that are lacking for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		2.16	1.00	Disagreed
3.	I am satisfied with the quality of the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		1.90	1.24	Disagreed
4.	When implementing the ECCE programs, I faced some issues related to the facilities.		2.00	1.34	Disagreed
5.	I believe the current facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs meet the requirements of the program curriculum.		2.24	1.00	Disagreed
6.	There are no additional facilities that should be provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		1.88	1.40	Disagreed
7.	I often use most of the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs.		2.79	0.51	Agreed
8.	I think the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs are safe and secure for the children.		2.90	0.63	Agreed
9.	The facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs enable children to learn effectively.		2.75	0.62	Agreed
10.	I believe availability of adequate facilities very important for the success of the ECCE programs.		3.02	0.43	Agreed

Source: Author’s Computation, 2023

The result in table 4 displays the mean and standard deviation of adequacy of facilities needed for implementation of the ECCE program among public primary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The results revealed that facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs are not adequate, as indicated on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. These items have their mean (\bar{X}) values lower than the criterion mean of 2.50 ($\bar{X} < 2.50$). The values of the standard deviation on the items indicate less variation in the responses of the respondents (teachers) due to the closeness of the values. This implies that the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs in public primary schools in Abuja are insufficient.

Discussion of Findings

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

The first finding of the study revealed that ECCE program's in public primary schools are beneficial to children in FCT Abuja. The reason for this might be that ECCE programs provide a strong foundation for lifelong learning, improve access to education, and enhance children's cognitive, social-emotional, and health outcomes. The finding confirms those of Shekarau (2014) who in his study noted that uniform programs related to early childhood education facilitates Human Development (HD) and can bring about development in education, health, social capital and equality that will help develop children that participate in the program even up to the future. This result corroborated the finding of Gorba (2012) which revealed that self-regulation, moral development, physical growth, personality development, and gender socialization are among the defining features of early childhood education. The implication of this finding is that ECCE programs in public primary schools may be an effective way to support children's development and prepare them for formal schooling.

Most interesting of the findings in this study is that majority of parents and society lacked awareness about the significance of ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja. The reason might be attributed to limited availability or accessibility of ECCE programs in public primary schools, particularly in underserved or remote areas, which may contribute to a lack of awareness among parents and society. This agrees with the findings of Reap (2010) that, the importance of Early Childhood has not caught the full attention of society. He went ahead to put that the lack of awareness and the uncertainty of parents on the influence of Early Child Education on the school readiness of their children lead many parents to place Early Child Education far from the top of the education priority list. The implication of lack of awareness about the significance of ECCE programs in public primary schools is parents may not prioritize their child's participation in these programs which leads to low participation rates, and schools may struggle to secure funding and resources for these programs due to limited support from parents and society, limiting their effectiveness.

It is important to note that the finding of study revealed that the majority of staff members possess the required skills to implement the ECCE programs in public primary schools. The possible reason could be that the staff members have received the necessary training and qualifications to implement the ECCE programs, and they have gained practical experience and developed the skills required through their work in the education sector. This aligns with the submission in an Issue Brief by National Governors Association Centre for Best Practices (2010) that the knowledge and skills of early childhood care providers and teachers are critical factors in their delivery of high-quality developmental and educational experiences to young children. In confirmation of this, Goble and Horm (2010) have submitted that whatever a person's profession is, the need for professional development is universal because professionals need to continually enrich their knowledge and increase their sense of professionalism over the course of their careers so as to implement current research based practice. The implication could lead to the successful implementation of the program, better learning outcomes for young children and improve the overall quality of education in public primary schools in Nigeria.

Similarly, findings of this study showed that the facilities provided for the implementation of the ECCE programs in public primary schools in Abuja are insufficient. The reason could be as a result of the fact Public primary schools may not receive adequate funding to support the development of ECCE programs which lead to a lack of resources such as teaching materials, toys, and equipment necessary for learning and development. The result of this study supports the findings of Good Planet Foundation (2013) on Nigeria that spending on essentials such as textbooks, instructional materials, in-service training, operations and maintenance is inadequate. The findings confirm those of Akinrotimi and Olowe (2016) who in their study found that Nigerian ECCE programs are ridiculously underfunded and could be linked to the low budgetary allocation to the education sector in the nation. The implication of this findings is that the effective implementation of the program may be hindered which in turn potentially limiting the quality of early childhood education provided to children.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the Early Childhood Care Education (ECCE) programs in public primary schools have not been effectively implemented. Equally, ECCE programs in public primary schools in FCT Abuja are perceived as beneficial to children. However, it could be concluded here that the lack of awareness among parents and society about the significance of these programs is a cause for concern. The majority of staff members possess the required skills to implement the program, but insufficient facilities hinder its implementation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. ECCE programs should be continued and expanded in public primary schools to provide more benefits to children. Additionally, efforts should be made to improve the quality and effectiveness of these programs through regular evaluation and training of teachers.

Qualitative Study on Implementation ... (Ahmed et. al., (2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570776>

2. Awareness campaigns and outreach programs be conducted to educate parents and society about the benefits of ECCE programs. This will help to increase participation and support for these programs which will lead to better outcomes for children.
3. Incentives such as recognition and career advancement opportunities could be provided to motivate staff members to continuously improve their skills and performance.
4. Government should conduct regular assessments to identify the gaps and areas for improvement in the facilities and resources for the ECCE programs in public primary schools and take necessary actions to address them.

References

- Akinrotimi, A. A., & Olowe, P. k., (2016). Challenges in Implementation of Early Childhood Education in Nigeria: The Way Forward. *Journal of Educational and Practice* 7(7), 119-1735.pdf
- Akinrotimi, A.A &Olowe, P.K. (2016).Challenges in implementation of early childhood education in Nigeria.The way forward.*Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(7), 33-38.
- Amadi, F.N.C. (2013). Challenges of early childhood care education in sustaining girl-child development in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* 4(5), 151-156
- Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2013). *National Policy on Education* (6th Edition), Abuja: NERDC Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2012). *National Policy on Education* (4th Ed.) Lagos: NERDC
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press
- Goble, C. B., &Horm, D. M. (2010). Take charge of your personal and professional development. NAEYC. Retrieved from <https://www.naeyc.org/files/yc/file/201011/GobleOnline1110.pdf>
- Maduewesi, E. J. (1999). *Early childhood Education: Theory and Practice*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Limited.
- National Policy on Education (2004). Federal Republic of Nigeria, Abuja, 4th edition
- NGA Centre for Best Practices (2010, February). Building an early childhood professional development system (Issue Brief). Retrieved from <http://www.nga.org/files/live/sites/NGA/files/pdf/1002EARLYCHILDPROFDEV.PDF>
- Odumosu, A. 2003, Combined Strategies in Curriculum Evaluation in Baiyelo (eds.) strategies of Managing Curriculum Evaluation, Lagos, solifem (Nig.) Co.
- Oduolowu, E. 2003, Current Status in Early Childhood Education in Nigeria, in Ehindero and Aladejana (eds.) Readings in Early Childhood and Universal Basic Education, Lagos, Lantern Books.
- Ogunode, N., Gregory D., &Abubakar, M. (2020). Assessment of Political Officeholders’ Attitudes Towards Planning of Education in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research in Developing Areas*, 1 (1), 68-79.
- Okewole, J. 2009, *Effects of Literature Circles and Classroom labeling Strategies on Nursery School Pupils’ Reading Skills*. Unpublished Master’s Thesis O.A.U. Ife.
- Olaleye, O.O., & Omotayo, K.A. (2009).Assessment of quality in early childhood education in Ekiti-state Nigeria. *World Applied science Journal* 7(5), 683-688. Retrieved from [http://www.idosi.org/wasj7\(5\)/19.pdf](http://www.idosi.org/wasj7(5)/19.pdf)
- Open Education Data (2020). Online: <http://www.fmebasic.intellisys.xyz/>
- REAP (2011). Early Child Education, viewed 11 November, 2011, http://reap.stanford.edu/docs/early_childhood_education.
- Shekarau, M. I. (2014). *Honourable minister of education foreword in early childhood development standards for Nigeria*. Abuja, Nigeria: FME.
- The Good Planet Foundation (2013). Accelerating progress to 2015. Nigeria. A report series to the UN Special Envoy for Global Education. Working Paper. Retrieved from <http://educationenvoy.org/wpcontent/uploads/2013/07/NIGERIA-UNSE-FINAL.pdf>
- UNESCO, (2007). *Nigeria early childhood care and education (ECCE) programmes; International Bureau of Education (IBE)*. Retrieved